

Step-Wise Goodness-of-Fit Testing for High-Dimensional Cross-Classified Tables

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Abstract

The Pearson and likelihood ratio statistics are commonly used to test goodness of fit for models applied to data from a multinomial distribution. The goodness-of-fit test based on Pearson's chi-squared statistic is sometimes considered to be a global test that gives little guidance to the source of poor fit when the null hypothesis is rejected, and it has also been recognized that the global test can often be outperformed in terms of power by focused or directional tests. In this paper, a sequence of test statistics is obtained by decomposing the Pearson statistic from the full table into orthogonal components defined on marginal distributions. These statistics are asymptotic independent, and can be used in a step-wise procedure, starting with higher-order marginals and proceeding to lower-order marginals. For a five-way table, there would be a test statistic for the 5th-order marginal, then fourth-order, then third-order and finally-second order. Although this step-wise procedure involves multiple testing, it can be shown to have higher power than the ordinary Pearson goodness-of-fit statistic, especially Higher-order marginals might be combined. An asymptotic distribution can be invoked for the statistics on lower-order marginals, but higher-order tables are sparse and a bootstrap method might be needed for the test on higher-order marginals. Since the test statistics are orthogonal components of the Pearson statistic, a test statistic for higher-order marginals can be obtained by subtracting the sum of the lower-order test statistics from the Pearson statistic. An application from epidemiology and psychometrics is presented.

Key Words: multivariate discrete distribution, overlapping cells, orthogonal components, composite null hypothesis

1 Introduction

The fit of a multinomial model is often assessed by testing the composite null hypothesis $H_o: \boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, where $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ is a T -dimensional vector of multinomial probabilities, and $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is a vector of the multinomial probabilities as a function of unique model parameters in the g -dimensional vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}$. For q variables, each with c categories, $T = c^q$. When the model parameters $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ are unknown and estimated, the null hypothesis $H_o: \boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is often tested with the Pearson-Fisher statistic:

$$X_{PF}^2 = n \sum_s z_s^2, \quad (1.1)$$

where

$$z_s = (\pi_s(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}))^{-\frac{1}{2}} (\hat{p}_s - \pi_s(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}})), \quad s = 1, \dots, c^q, \quad (1.2)$$

and where

$\hat{p}_s = \frac{n_s}{n}$ is element s of $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$, the vector of multinomial proportions,

$n_s =$ element s of \mathbf{n} , the vector of observed frequencies,

$n =$ total sample size $= \sum_{s=1}^T n_s$,

$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} =$ parameter estimator vector,

$\pi_s(\boldsymbol{\beta}) =$ the expected proportion for cell s , and

$\pi_s(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) =$ estimated expected proportion for cell s .

The goodness-of-fit test based on Pearson's Chi-squared statistic is sometimes considered to be a global test that gives little guidance to the source of poor fit when the null hypothesis is rejected, and it has also been recognized that the global test can often be outperformed in terms of power by focused or directional tests. The focus on second-order marginals for cross-classified tables is supported by the findings of Salomaa (1990).

Our approach, in the tradition of Lancaster (1969), Mirvaliev (1987), and Rayner and Best (1989), decomposes the Pearson statistic from a full cross-classified table, where variables have $c \geq 2$ categories, into orthogonal components. higher power to detect lack of fit while maintaining good Type I error control even if the joint frequencies are very sparse, as will be shown in simulation results; theoretical results will establish that Also calculations of $GFfit_{\perp}^{(ij)}$ statistics is computationally stable.

When data are a table of counts formed by the cross-classification of a large number of variables, Pearson's Chi-square and the likelihood ratio statistic may have low power and inaccurate Type I error level due to sparseness (Koehler, 1986; Koehler & Larntz, 1980; Agresti & Yang, 1987). In order to overcome the effects of sparse frequencies, several omnibus statistics have been proposed that focus on lower-order marginal distributions of the joint variables rather than the full joint distribution. Reiser (1996, 2008) de-

veloped omnibus test statistics focused on lower-order marginals for models fit to cross-classified binary variables by using orthogonal components of the Pearson-Fisher statistic.

2 Linear Combinations of Joint Frequencies

A traditional goodness-of-fit approach for a multinomial model fit to a cross-classified table uses the joint frequencies to calculate a test statistic. This section presents a transformation from joint proportions or frequencies to marginal proportions which are used to develop statistics on lower-order marginals presented in Section 3.2.

2.1 Marginal Probabilities

Marginal proportions for a contingency table can be obtained by a linear combination of the joint proportions. The relationship can be shown by using 0's and 1's to code the levels of categorical response variables, $Y_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, q$, where $q \geq 2$ and Y_i has $c \geq 2$ response categories. A $q(c - 1)$ -dimensional vector of 0's and 1's, can indicate a specific cell from the contingency table formed by the cross-classification of q response variables. Then a $T = c^q$ -dimensional set of response patterns can be generated by varying the levels of the q^{th} variable most rapidly, the $q^{th} - 1$ variable next, etc. Define \mathbf{V} as the T by $q(c - 1)$ matrix with response patterns as rows.

For $q = 3$ and $c = 2$, \mathbf{V} is the familiar matrix of response patterns:

$$\mathbf{V} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.1)$$

Although the order of the columns of \mathbf{V} is arbitrary, the ordering described above is a natural ordering that will produce rows such that the binary numbers represented by the patterns are in ascending order. More detail on generating the matrix \mathbf{V} is given in Reiser, Cagnone and Zhu (2023).

For $q = 3$ and $c = 3$,

$$\mathbf{V}_{27 \times 6} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.2)$$

2.2 One-to-One Transformation

The summation across the frequencies associated with the response patterns to obtain the marginal proportions represents a linear transformation of the frequencies in the multinomial vector $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ which can be implemented via multiplication by a certain incidence matrix, denoted here generically by the symbol \mathbf{H} . The symbol $\mathbf{H}_{[t]}$ denotes the transformation matrix that would produce marginals of order t . The symbol $\mathbf{H}_{[t:u]}$, $t \leq u \leq q$, denotes the transformation matrix that would produce marginals from order t up to and including order u . Furthermore, $\mathbf{H}_{[t]} \equiv \mathbf{H}_{[t:t]}$, and $\mathbf{H} \equiv \mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$. More detail on generating the matrix \mathbf{H} is given in Reiser, Cagnone and Zhu (2023). For first-order marginal proportions, $\mathbf{H}_{[1]} = \mathbf{V}'$.

For higher-order marginal proportions, the rows of \mathbf{H} can be obtained as Hadamard products among the columns of \mathbf{V} , as shown in Reiser, Cagnone and Zhu (2023). The second-order marginal proportions for variables Y_i and Y_j can be obtained by employing the matrix $\mathbf{H}_{[2]}$, and the third-order marginal proportions for variables Y_i , Y_j , and Y_k can be obtained by employing the matrix $\mathbf{H}_{[3]}$. Then, for example,

$$\mathbf{H}_{[1:3]} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{[1]} \\ \dots \\ \mathbf{H}_{[2]} \\ \dots \\ \mathbf{H}_{[3]} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.3)$$

A general matrix $\mathbf{H}_{[t:u]}$ to obtain marginals of any order can be defined in a similar fashion by using Hadamard products among the columns of \mathbf{V} . $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$ gives a mapping from the c^q joint proportions to the set

of $(c^q - 1)$ linearly independent marginal proportions:

$$\mathbf{\Pi} = \mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}\boldsymbol{\pi}, \quad (2.4)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{\Pi} = & (\pi^{(1)}(2), \pi^{(1)}(3), \dots, \pi^{(1)}(c), \pi^{(2)}(2), \pi^{(2)}(3), \dots, \pi^{(2)}(c), \dots, \pi^{(q)}(c), \\ & \pi^{(12)}(2, 2), \pi^{(12)}(2, 3), \dots, \pi^{(q-1, q)}(c, c), \pi^{(1, 1, 2)}(2, 2, 2), \dots, \pi^{(q-2, q-1, q)}(c, c, c) \\ & \dots \pi^{(1, 2, 3, \dots, q)}(c, c, c, \dots, c))' \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

is the vector of linearly independent marginal proportions (Bartholomew, 1987). The vector of marginal proportions under the model $\boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is then given by

$$\mathbf{\Pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta}), \quad (2.6)$$

As constructed, the first column of $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$ is a column of 0's, and can be omitted along with the first element of $\boldsymbol{\pi}$. So define $\ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{[1:q]} = (\mathbf{h}_2 \mathbf{h}_3 \dots \mathbf{h}_{c^q})$ and $\ddot{\boldsymbol{\pi}} = (\pi_2, \pi_3, \dots, \pi_{c^q})$, where \mathbf{h}_f is column f , $f = 2, \dots, c^q$, from $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$, and π_f is element f of $\boldsymbol{\pi}$. $\ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{[1:q]}$ is now a $c^q - 1$ by $c^q - 1$ full rank matrix. The location of the column of 0's in $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$ is arbitrary, but it appears in column 1 under the ordering defined above. Then

$$\mathbf{\Pi} = \ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{[1:q]}\ddot{\boldsymbol{\pi}} \quad (2.7)$$

is equivalent to expression 2.4, and the transformation from joint proportions to marginal proportions can be seen to be a one-to-one transformation from $\Re^{c^q-1} \rightarrow \Re^{c^q-1}$. Throughout this paper, $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}\boldsymbol{\pi}$ could be replaced by $\ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{[1:q]}\ddot{\boldsymbol{\pi}}$.

3 Orthogonal Components of X_{PF}^2

Orthogonal components of X_{PF}^2 defined on marginal proportions were presented by Reiser (2008) for $q \geq 3$ categorical variables with $c = 2$ categories and by Reiser, Cagnone and Zhu (2023) for $q \geq 3$ categorical variables with $c \geq 2$.

3.1 Equivalence of X_{PF}^2 and a Quadratic Form on Marginals

Define the unstandardized residual $r_s = \hat{p}_s - \pi_s(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}})$, and denote the T -dimensional vector of unstandardized residuals as \mathbf{r} with element r_s . A vector of simple residuals for marginals of any order may be defined such that $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{H}(\hat{\mathbf{p}} - \boldsymbol{\pi}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}})) = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{r}$. Let X_{T-g-1}^2 be a quadratic form statistic defined on marginal proportions. As mentioned earlier, g is the number of model parameters to be estimated. This section gives the conditions under which X_{T-g-1}^2 is equivalent to X_{PF}^2 . Define the two quadratic form statistics as follows:

$$X_{PF}^2 = n\mathbf{r}'D(\boldsymbol{\pi}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}))^{-1}\mathbf{r}, \text{ and} \quad (3.1)$$

$$X_{T-g-1}^2 = n\mathbf{r}'\mathbf{H}'\hat{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}_e^{-1}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{e}'\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_e^{-1}\mathbf{e} \quad (3.2)$$

where,

$$n^{\frac{1}{2}}\mathbf{r} \xrightarrow{d} MVN(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{\Omega}_{\mathbf{r}}) \quad (3.3)$$

$$\mathbf{\Omega}_{\mathbf{r}} = (D(\boldsymbol{\pi}) - \boldsymbol{\pi}\boldsymbol{\pi}' - \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{G}') \quad (3.4)$$

$$\mathbf{\Omega}_{\mathbf{e}} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{\Omega}_{\mathbf{r}}\mathbf{H}' \quad (3.5)$$

$$D(\boldsymbol{\pi}) = \text{diagonal matrix with } (s, s) \text{ element equal to } \pi_s(\boldsymbol{\beta}) \quad (3.6)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = D(\boldsymbol{\pi})^{-1/2} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\beta}}, \quad \mathbf{G} = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\beta}}, \quad (3.7)$$

$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{\mathbf{e}} = n^{-1}\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}_{\mathbf{e}}$, and $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}_{\mathbf{e}} = \mathbf{\Omega}_{\mathbf{e}}$ evaluated at $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\pi}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\widehat{\boldsymbol{\beta}})$. See Haberman (1993) for (3.3) and (3.4). $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{T-g-1}$, is a $T - g - 1$ by c^q partition of $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$, as defined in Section 2, with g rows deleted in order to render $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{\mathbf{e}}$ full rank by accounting for estimated parameters of the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$. For some models, any g rows can be deleted. For other models, such as a hierarchical log-linear model where some marginals are exactly fit, the g rows to be deleted are determined in whole or in part by features of the model. Alternatively, it is possible to define and calculate X_{T-g-1}^2 without deleting rows from $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$, but then a generalized inverse would be needed for $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{\mathbf{e}}$. We use the expected information matrix $(\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})$ because we are interested in components of the X_{PF}^2 statistic.

Consider the full rank matrix $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{T-g-1}$, as defined above. Then define $\mathbf{H}^* = \mathbf{F}'\mathbf{H}$, where \mathbf{F} is the upper triangular matrix such that $\mathbf{F}'\mathbf{\Omega}_{\mathbf{e}}\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{I}$. $\mathbf{F} = (\mathbf{C}')^{-1}$, where \mathbf{C} is the Cholesky factor of $\mathbf{\Omega}_{\mathbf{e}}$. Premultiplication by $(\mathbf{C}')^{-1}$ orthonormalises the matrix \mathbf{H} relative to the matrix $(D(\boldsymbol{\pi}) - \boldsymbol{\pi}\boldsymbol{\pi}' - \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{G}')$. \mathbf{H}^* has full row rank.

Then from Reiser (2008),

$$X_{T-g-1}^2 = n\mathbf{r}'\mathbf{H}'\widehat{\mathbf{F}}\widehat{\mathbf{F}}^{-1}\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}_{\mathbf{e}}^{-1}(\widehat{\mathbf{F}}')^{-1}\widehat{\mathbf{F}}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{r} = n\mathbf{r}'\mathbf{H}'\widehat{\mathbf{F}}(\widehat{\mathbf{F}}'\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}_{\mathbf{e}}\widehat{\mathbf{F}})^{-1}\widehat{\mathbf{F}}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{r} = n\mathbf{r}'(\widehat{\mathbf{H}}^*)'\widehat{\mathbf{H}}^*\mathbf{r}, \quad (3.8)$$

where $\widehat{\mathbf{H}}^* = \mathbf{H}^*(\widehat{\boldsymbol{\beta}})$.

Now define

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\widehat{\mathbf{F}}'\mathbf{H}\mathbf{r} = n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\widehat{\mathbf{H}}^*\mathbf{r} \quad (3.9)$$

where $\widehat{\mathbf{F}}$ is the matrix \mathbf{F} evaluated at $\boldsymbol{\beta} = \widehat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$. Then from expression 3.8,

$$X_{T-g-1}^2 = \widehat{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}'\widehat{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = \sum_{\ell=1}^{j=T-g-1} \widehat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2. \quad (3.10)$$

Theorem 1. *If \mathbf{H} is a $T - g - 1$ by T matrix with rank = $(T - g - 1)$*

$$X_{PF}^2 = X_{T-g-1}^2 \quad (3.11)$$

Proof: Reiser (2008); Reiser, Cagnone and Zhu (2022). Theorem 1 is a special case of results in Section 7.2 of Rayner and Best (1969). From properties of the Cholesky factor, $\widehat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2$, $\ell = 1, \dots, (T - g - 1)$, are orthogonal components of X_{PF}^2 when $c \geq 2$, and they have a sequential property. Orthonormalization of goodness-of-fit diagnostics using the Cholesky factor has been considered for other statistical models.

Houseman et al. (2004), Jacqmin-Gadda et al. (2007), and Verbeke and Molenberghs (2009) have proposed and studied the *Cholesky residual*. $\widehat{\mathbf{H}}^* \mathbf{r}$ is essentially a vector of Cholesky residuals on the marginals.

Theorem 2. *Assuming the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is identified, under the $H_0 : \boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, the regularity conditions given by Birch (1964) and sparse asymptotics presented in Simonoff (1987),*

The elements $\hat{\gamma}_\ell^2 \xrightarrow{d} \chi_1^2$ and are asymptotically independent random variables.

Proof:

Under the regularity conditions given by Birch (1964), and assuming the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is identified, $n\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}\mathbf{e} \xrightarrow{P} \boldsymbol{\Omega}\mathbf{e}$ and $\mathbf{e} \xrightarrow{d} MVN(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}\mathbf{e})$, where $\boldsymbol{\xi} = \mathbf{H}(\boldsymbol{\pi} - \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta}))$. Then, since \mathbf{e} is a linear combination of the elements of \mathbf{r} , $\widehat{\mathbf{H}}^* \mathbf{r}$ has asymptotic covariance matrix $\mathbf{F}'\boldsymbol{\Omega}\mathbf{e}\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{I}_{T-g-1}$, and the elements $\hat{\gamma}_\ell^2 \xrightarrow{d} \chi_1^2$ and are asymptotically independent random variables.

A computational method from Reiser (2008) produces very reliable results by obtaining orthogonal components as the sequential sum of squares from a weighted orthogonal regression. The method is applicable when $c \geq 2$ and is used to calculate components for the application in Section 4. The regression coefficients themselves have no meaning, and the regression is simply a method to obtain orthogonal components, an alternative to applying the Cholesky factor or Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization.

3.2 Partition of Pearson's X^2 Statistic

Partition X_{PF}^2 into partial sums of components:

$$X_{PF}^2 = \hat{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}'\hat{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = \sum_{\ell=1}^{\ell=T-(g-q(c-1))-1} \hat{\gamma}_\ell^2,$$

and then

$$\begin{aligned} X_{PF}^2 = & \sum_{\ell=1}^{\ell=\binom{q}{2}(c-1)^2} \hat{\gamma}_\ell^2 + \sum_{\ell=\binom{q}{2}(c-1)^2+1}^{\ell=\binom{q}{2}(c-1)^2+\binom{q}{3}(c-1)^3} \hat{\gamma}_\ell^2 + \dots \\ & + \sum_{\ell=\sum_{k=2}^{q-1} \binom{q}{k}(c-1)^k}^{\ell=\sum_{k=2}^{q-1} \binom{q}{k}(c-1)^k} \hat{\gamma}_\ell^2 + \sum_{\ell=\sum_{k=2}^{q-1} \binom{q}{k}(c-1)^k+1}^{\ell=T-(g-q(c-1))-1} \hat{\gamma}_\ell^2 \end{aligned}$$

As in Reiser, Cagnone and Zhu (2023), define test statistics $X_{[t|u]}^2$ on the partial sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
X_{[2]}^2 &= \sum_{\ell=1}^{\ell=\binom{q}{2}(c-1)^2} \hat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2 \\
X_{[3|2]}^2 &= \sum_{\ell=\binom{q}{2}(c-1)^2+1}^{\ell=\binom{q}{2}(c-1)^2+\binom{q}{3}(c-1)^3} \hat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2 \\
&\vdots \\
X_{[(q-1)|(q-2),(q-3),\dots,2]}^2 &= \sum_{\ell=\sum_{k=2}^{q-1} \binom{q}{k}(c-1)^k}^{\ell=\sum_{k=2}^{q-2} \binom{q}{k}(c-1)^{k+1}} \hat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2 \\
X_{[(q)|(q-1),(q-2),\dots,2]}^2 &= \sum_{\ell=\sum_{k=2}^{q-1} \binom{q}{k}(c-1)^{k+1}}^{\ell=T-(g-q(c-1))-1} \hat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2
\end{aligned}$$

$X_{[2]}^2$ is a statistic on the second-order marginals. $X_{[3|2]}^2$ is a statistic on the third-order marginals given that components for $X_{[2]}^2$ have already been extracted from X_{PF}^2 . The sequence of statistics continues until $X_{[(q)|(q-1),(q-2),\dots,2]}^2$ which is a statistic on the q^{th} -order marginals given that components for all lower-order marginals have already been extracted from X_{PF}^2 . Under the null hypothesis stated in Theorem 2, partial sums of the $\hat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2$ have an asymptotic Chi-square distribution because the $\hat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2$ are asymptotic independent Chi-square. Degrees of freedom is equal to the number of non-zero components in the sum. However, as with X_{PF}^2 , the asymptotic distribution for $\hat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2$ may fail if the marginal frequencies used to calculate $\hat{\gamma}_{\ell}^2$ are sparse. Components identically equal to zero may be produced by restrictions on the marginals included in $X_{[t|u]}^2$ or linear dependencies of rows in $\mathbf{H}_{[t|u]}$ on the model matrix for $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, both of which would be known from theory. More details on the degrees of freedom are given in Reiser (2008). $X_{[t|u]}^2$ is essentially a version of the score statistic from Rayner and Best (1989).

Then,

Result 3.1: Assuming the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is identified for $q \geq 3$ and $g \geq q(c-1)$, with at least $(c-1)$ unknown intercept or first-order parameters for each variable in the cross-classified table, and that $q(c-1)$ of the orthogonal components for first-order marginals are fixed at zero by eliminating the $\mathbf{H}_{[1]}$ partition from \mathbf{H} , then

$$X_{PF}^2 = X_{[2]}^2 + X_{[3|2]}^2 + X_{[4|3,2]}^2 + \dots + X_{[q|(q-1),(q-2),\dots,2]}^2 \quad (3.12)$$

The result follows because the $X_{[t|u]}^2$ are partial sums of the non-zero $T - g - 1$ components of X_{PF}^2 . Since expression (3.12) decomposes the entire X_{PF}^2 statistic into components, rows of \mathbf{H} that correspond to estimated parameters of the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ should be considered, as mentioned in Section 3.1. The joint proportions of a c^q table can be transformed to $c^q - 1$ marginal proportions, but g of these marginal proportions will be exactly fit under a model with g estimated parameters, and the orthogonal components for the Pearson-Fisher statistic on these marginals will be identically equal to zero. So for Result 3.1, while $\mathbf{H}_{[1]}$ has

been deleted from $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$, the $\hat{\gamma}_\ell^2$ may contain additional components that are identically equal to zero, but the components that are identically equal to zero can be eliminated from $\hat{\gamma}$ by deleting a total of g linearly independent rows from $\mathbf{H}_{[1:q]}$. The rows to be deleted will depend on the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$.

Because of the sequential property of the orthogonal components, higher-order statistics may be pooled. For example:

$$X_{PF}^2 = X_{[2]}^2 + X_{[3|2]}^2 + X_{[4,5,\dots,q|3,2]}^2 \quad (3.13)$$

Other test statistics on lower-order marginals have been developed by Bartholomew and Leung (2002), Tollenaar and Mooijaart (2003), and Maydeu-Olivares and Joe (2005, 2006), but these statistics are not components of the Pearson-Fisher statistic.

3.3 Step-Wise Testing

The power of the test on a simple null hypothesis $H_0 : \boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}_0$ using the Pearson test statistic will almost always be diluted in a high-dimensional table because, from the point of view of partitioning X_{PF}^2 into $X_{[t|u]}^2$ statistics, most of the degrees of freedom for the test are used in looking for lack of fit in higher-order marginals. Similarly, the power of the test on the composite null hypothesis $H_0 : \boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ using X_{PF}^2 as the test statistic will almost be diluted in a high-dimensional table for the same reason. The power of the test is diluted when the magnitude of the noncentrality parameter for the test statistic is small relative to the degrees of freedom. The magnitude of the degrees of freedom for X_{PF}^2 associated with higher-order marginals increases exponentially for a $T = c^q$ table. Therefore, it may be possible in many, if not most, applications when testing a model fit to a high-dimensional cross-classified table to obtain higher power by actually foregoing the omnibus test using X_{PF}^2 and using instead a step-wise procedure on the components of X_{PF}^2 as defined in the previous section. The relative power will be determined by the partitioning of the noncentrality parameter as defined in the subsequent section of this paper. A multiple decision rule should be used in order to maintain overall probability of Type I error in the step-wise procedure since it would not be preceded by a single global test.

The specific tests in a step-wise procedure will depend on the application. The steps of the tests are in reverse order to the order of extraction of orthogonal components, as in sequential sum of squares in a regression. Higher power may be obtained if components for higher-order marginals are pooled. The following sequence of hypotheses is an example of the procedure that would pool all components for fourth-order marginals, then test on third-order marginals, and then test on second-order marginals. The focus of the testing is on lower-order marginals:

Step 1: $H_0 : \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, where $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{[4,5,\dots,q|3,2]}$

Step 2: $H_0 : \mathbf{H}_{[3|2]}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}_{[3|2]}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$

Step 3: $H_0 : \mathbf{H}_{[2]}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}_{[2]}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$

The overall probability of Type I error can be controlled by using the Bonferroni correction, but since the tests are asymptotic independent, the alpha level for each test can be determined from

$$\alpha = 1 - (1 - \alpha^*)^b,$$

where α^* = probability of Type I error each test, and b = number of tests. As in a testing a regression model using sequential sum of squares, testing is terminated when a null hypothesis is rejected. Using the

Bonferroni inequality in this setting, $\alpha^* = 0.0167$ for each of the three tests.

In this second example, components for fourth-order marginals and above are pooled, and components for second-, and third-order marginals are also pooled, resulting in two tests in the step-wise procedure. The focus of the testing is on pooled second- and third-order marginals:

Step 1: $H_0 : \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, where $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{[4,5,\dots,q|3,2]}$

Step 2: $H_0 : \mathbf{H}_{[3:2]}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}_{[3:2]}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$

$\alpha^* = 0.025$ can be used on each test in the step-wise procedure to control overall probability of Type I error.

In this third example, there are only two tests in the step-wise procedure, and the focus is on the second-order marginals.

Step 1: $H_0 : \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, where $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{[3,4,5,\dots,q|3,2]}$

Step 2: $H_0 : \mathbf{H}_{[2]}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}_{[2]}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$

$\alpha^* = 0.025$ can be used on each test in the step-wise procedure to control overall probability of Type I error.

There is a trade-off between the number of tests in the step-wise procedure and overall power of the testing. Including more tests in the step-wise procedure will cause each test and the procedure to be more conservative because of the more stringent α^* levels needed to control the overall probability of Type I error. If too many tests are included in the step-wise procedure, the procedure will have lower power than the omnibus test using X_{PF}^2 .

The logic of testing the fit of the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ on lower-order marginals is that if the model has an adequate fit on the joint frequencies, then it must also fit the marginal frequency tables. Hence if the null hypothesis $H_0 : \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is rejected, then the null hypothesis $H_0 : \boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ should be rejected. However, if the null hypothesis $H_0 : \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ on lower-order marginals is not rejected, it does not necessarily follow that the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is an adequate model for the joint frequencies, and a decision about the fit of the model is difficult. The test of the null hypothesis $H_0 : \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ on second-order marginals, for example, is equivalent to a test on the joint frequencies in the sense that do not reject $H_0 : \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ implies that the model is an adequate fit for the joint frequencies only if the table of joint frequencies is *collapsible* to the table of second-order marginals (Reiser, 1996). Several authors (Reiser, 1996, 2008; Bartholomew and Leung, 2002; Tollenaar and Mooijaart, 2003; and Maydeu-Olivares and Joe, 2005, 2006) have proposed a test of fit for the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ directly on the second-order marginals and ignoring model fit on higher-order marginals. This approach is somewhat justified by an important study where Salomaa (1990) found that lack of fit for latent variable models fit to questionnaire data can primarily be detected in the second-order marginals. However, it cannot generally be expected that lack of fit will always be found in the second-order marginals especially for different models in other applications such as longitudinal studies of categorical variables or studies of the influence of genes where third- and fourth-order interactions could be expected. See Reiser (2008) for an example. Hence the need for a step-wise procedure that does not ignore higher-order marginals.

For goodness-of-fit testing in high-dimensional tables, there is a concomitant problem of *sparseness* in the joint frequencies. The asymptotic approximation may not be valid if the joint frequencies are sparse. Statistical tests using the asymptotic approximation for test statistics on lower-order marginals have very good performance for Type I error rate and power even when the full data table is sparse. Tests on higher-order marginals, however, may require an alternative method such as the parametric bootstrap to determine a valid *p-value* because of sparseness that will appear in higher-order marginals when the joint frequencies are sparse.

3.4 Asymptotic Power

Asymptotic power of the Pearson statistic for a composite null hypothesis can be considered by using a sequence of local alternative,

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}_n = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) + \boldsymbol{\delta}/\sqrt{n}, \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\pi}_n$ is the vector of true probabilities indexed by the sample size n .

Under $H_a : \boldsymbol{\pi} \neq \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, X_{PF}^2 has a limiting noncentral chi-square distribution with noncentrality parameter λ , where

$$\lambda = \boldsymbol{\delta}' \text{Diag}[\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\theta})]^{-1} \boldsymbol{\delta},$$

and $df = T - g - 1$ (Mitra, 1958). Then,

$$\lambda = \boldsymbol{\delta}' \text{Diag}[\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\theta})]^{-1} \boldsymbol{\delta} = \boldsymbol{\delta}' \mathbf{H}' \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e^{-1} \mathbf{H} \boldsymbol{\delta} \quad (11)$$

Based on the right-hand side of this expression, decompose the noncentrality parameter into orthogonal components associated with marginals of order 1 to q in a manner very close to the earlier decomposition of X_{PF}^2

Using a Cholesky decomposition, let

$$\boldsymbol{\zeta} = (\mathbf{F}') \mathbf{H} \boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{H}^* \boldsymbol{\delta}, \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{H}^* are as defined earlier. Then $\lambda = \boldsymbol{\zeta}' \boldsymbol{\zeta}$, and orthogonal components are ζ_j^2 , where ζ_j is an element of $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$.

The noncentrality parameter may be partitioned among the components of X_{PF}^2 . Invoking a principle of parsimony, or Occam's razor, components on first- or second-order marginals are extracted first, followed by higher-order marginals in lexical order. That is, lack of fit should be attributed to lower-order associations if possible rather than looking for more complex explanations. For a test of a simple null hypothesis $H_0 : \boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}_0$ on a high-dimensional table, the component of the noncentrality parameter associated with first-order marginals may be large, and the test on first-order marginals may be powerful. For a composite null hypotheses $H_0 : \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ on a high-dimensional table, however, a test of fit on the first-order marginals will generally have low power when the model places constraints on association among the variables.

The noncentrality parameter for $X_{[2]}^2$ is given by

$$\lambda_{[2]} = \mathbf{H}_{[2]}^* \boldsymbol{\delta} = n \sum_{j=1}^{j=\binom{q}{2}(c-1)^2} \zeta_j^2$$

The relative power of proposed tests on marginals will depend on the magnitude of the component of the noncentrality parameter relative to degrees of freedom. The degrees of freedom for a component of X_{PF}^2 will depend on the model. If there are no constraints on the second-order marginals, the degrees of freedom for a test using $X_{[2]}^2$ will be $\min(T - g - 1, \binom{q}{2}(c - 1)^2)$. For $q = 7$ and $c = 4$, $\binom{q}{2}(c - 1)^2 = 189$.

The noncentrality parameter for $X_{[3|2]}^2$ is given by

$$\lambda_{[3|2]} = \mathbf{H}_{[3|2]}^* \boldsymbol{\delta}.$$

If there are no constraints on the third order marginals, and if $T - g - 1 > \binom{g}{2}(c - 1)^3$ the degrees of freedom for a test using $X_{[3|2]}^2$ will be $\min(T - g - 1 - \binom{g}{2}(c - 1)^2, \binom{g}{3}(c - 1)^3)$. For $q = 7$ and $c = 4$, $\binom{7}{3}(c - 1)^2 = 945$. It is apparent that the power of the test on third-order marginals will be diluted by the larger degrees of freedom unless $\lambda_{[3|2]}$ is relatively large. At the fourth-order marginals for $q = 7$ and $c = 4$, $\binom{7}{4}(c - 1)^4 = 2,835$, and a test using $X_{[4|3,2]}^2$ will also be diluted unless $\lambda_{[4|3,2]}$ is relatively large. For $q = 7$, degrees of freedom for $X_{[t|u]}^2$ above the fourth-order marginals continue to increase exponentially, and the component of the noncentrality parameter is likely to be very small in magnitude, producing a test with low power for the higher-order marginals.

For a goodness-of-fit test on a cross-classified tables with $q = 7$ and $c = 4$, X_{PF}^2 has $16,383 - g$ degrees of freedom. From the point of view of partitioning into $X_{[t|u]}^2$ statistics, most of those degrees of freedom are used in looking for lack of fit in higher-order marginals where the components of the noncentrality parameter are small, relative to degrees of freedom, when calculated in a sequential manner. This is the cause of low power for X_{PF}^2 when testing a model fit to a high-dimensional cross-classified table.

4 Application to Depression Symptoms

4.1 Application

The step-wise procedure was used to evaluate the fit of a one factor generalized linear latent variable model (GLLVM) to responses given to questions related to the psychiatric condition depression. Depression symptoms are heterogeneous in view of a one-dimensional model (Reiser, 1989), so most of the symptom questions chosen for this example are more homogeneous in that they ask respondents about how they “felt.” The data used in this example consist of the responses from 294 adults to the following seven depression symptom questions:

- (1) “I felt that I could not shake off the blues even with the help of my family and friends,”
- (2) “I felt hopeful about the future,”
- (3) “I felt that everything was an effort,”
- (4) “I felt lonely,”
- (5) “I felt fearful,”
- (6) “I thought my life had become a failure,” and
- (7) “I felt that people disliked me.”

The four response categories, ordered from most to least severe, were (1) “most or all of the time,” (2) “occasionally or a moderate amount of time,” (3) “some or little of the time,” and (4) “rarely or none of the time.” The source of the data is Afifi and Clark (1984), and the data is also reproduced in Sharma (1995). Fifty of the 294 sample members were classified as depressed based the Center for Epidemiologic Studies

Depression Scale (CESD), which would give a rate that is higher than the prevalence of about 7% for depression in the general U.S. population of adults (NIMH, 2019). The marginal proportions for the severe level of all of the symptoms in the sample are very low, at five percent or less, so the 4^7 cross-classified table is very sparse with a large number of cells that have count 0.

4.2 GLLVM

GLLVM is a latent variable response model for categorical variables with two or more graded categories and has features of a proportional odds model. Let $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_q)'$ be the vector of q ordinal observed variables, each of them having c_i categories. Thus there are $\prod_{i=1}^q c_i$ cells, also called response patterns in the cross-classified table. Response pattern s is indicated as $\mathbf{y}_s = (y_1 = a_1, y_2 = a_2, \dots, y_q = a_q)'$, where a_i is the value of the i^{th} observed variable ($a_i = 1, \dots, c_i$ and $i = 1, \dots, q$). Let $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p)'$ be the vector of p continuous latent variables. Then the probability of response pattern s is given by

$$\pi_s(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{y}_s | \boldsymbol{\beta}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \cdots \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{y}_s | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{x}) f(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}, \quad s = 1, 2, \dots, T \quad (4.1)$$

where $f(\mathbf{x})$ is the density function of \mathbf{X} , and the multiple integral is over dimension p .

The conditional probability of \mathbf{Y} given \mathbf{x} expresses conditional independence:

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{y}_s | \mathbf{x}) = \prod_{i=1}^q \pi_{a_{is}}^{(i)}(\mathbf{x}) = \prod_{i=1}^q (\eta_{a_{is}}^{(i)} - \eta_{a_{i-1,s}}^{(i)}) \quad (4.2)$$

where $\eta_{a_i}^{(i)} = \pi_1^{(i)}(\mathbf{x}) + \pi_2^{(i)}(\mathbf{x}) + \dots + \pi_{a_i}^{(i)}(\mathbf{x})$ is the probability of a response in category a_i or lower on the variable i , and $\pi_{a_i}^{(i)}(\mathbf{x})$ is the probability of a response in category a_i on the variable i . Logistic regression is used to model the interrelationship between $\eta_{a_i}^{(i)}$ and the latent variables:

$$\log\left(\frac{\eta_r^{(i)}}{1 - \eta_r^{(i)}}\right) = \beta_{i0}(r) - \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_{ij} x_j,$$

$r = 1, \dots, c_{i-1}$, where c_i is the number of categories for variable i , $\beta_{i0}(r)$ and β_{ij} are the parameters of the model. $\beta_{i0}(r)$ is an intercept and β_{ij} is the j^{th} slope for variable i . The intercepts should satisfy the condition $\beta_{i0}(1) \leq \beta_{i0}(2) \leq \dots \leq \beta_{i0}(c_i)$. The integrals are approximated through the Gauss-Hermite quadrature method.

4.3 Results

Fitting GLLVM with one continuous latent factor, testing the null hypothesis $H_0: \boldsymbol{\pi} = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, $X_{PF}^2 = 12,941.12$, with $p\text{-value} = 0.874$ using the parametric bootstrap because of sparseness in the joint frequencies. The power of the omnibus global test is diluted because the test statistic on the joint frequencies is equivalent to including all higher-order marginals.

Instead of the global test, partitioning X_{PF}^2 for *pre-planned focused* step-wise GOF tests:

$$X_{PF}^2 = X_{[2]}^2 + X_{[3|2]}^2 + X_{[4|3,2]}^2 + X_{[5|4,3,2]}^2 + X_{[6:7|5,4,3,2]}^2 \quad (4.3)$$

$$= 236.29 + 879.62 + 2,559.35 + 4,297.37 + 4,968.49 \quad (4.4)$$

$$= X_{[2]}^2 + X_{[3:7|2]}^2 \quad (4.5)$$

$$= 236.29 + 12,704.83 \quad (4.6)$$

Then, Step 1: For the null hypothesis $H_o: \mathbf{H}_{[3:7|2]}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}_{[3:7|2]}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, $X_{[3:7|2]}^2 = 12,704.83$, with *p-value* = 0.67 using the parametric bootstrap due to sparseness in higher-order marginals. This test is still diluted.

Next, Step 2: For the null hypothesis $H_o: \mathbf{H}_{[2]}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}_{[2]}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, $X_{[2]}^2 = 236.29$. Applying the asymptotic approximation, $X_{[2]}^2$ is distributed approximately Chi-square on 189 degrees of freedom, with *p-value* = 0.0111. Using $\alpha^* = 0.05/2 = 0.025$, reject H_o at this step and conclude that the model $\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ does not fit the responses to the seven depression symptoms because if the model has an adequate fit to the joint frequencies, it must also fit the marginal frequency tables. In this application, step-wise testing with focus on the second-order marginals detected lack of fit when the global test using X_{PF}^2 did not detect the lack of fit. The results from the two tests are different because X_{PF}^2 has low power for detecting lack of fit for this model in this high-dimensional cross-classified table. We compare the step-wise result to the result from the test using X_{PF}^2 , but researchers may choose to simply forgo the omnibus test using X_{PF}^2 in this type of application because it will have low power unless the noncentrality parameter for the omnibus test is very large.

Alternatively, instead of pooling $X_{[3|2]}^2$ with the higher-order statistics, the asymptotic approximation may be valid for $X_{[3|2]}^2$ on 945 degrees of freedom. A third step could have been included (if pre-planned): For the null hypothesis $H_o: \mathbf{H}_{[3|2]}\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mathbf{H}_{[3|2]}\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, $X_{[3|2]}^2 = 879.62$, with *p-value* = 0.936. The test on the third-order marginals is already diluted.

The $X_{[2]}^2$ statistic can be further partitioned into $GFfit_{\perp}^{(ij)}$ orthogonal components that can be used as lack-of-fit diagnostics (Reiser, Cagnone and Zhu, 2023). Examining the $GFfit_{\perp}^{(ij)}$ diagnostics for this example, the lack of fit for the one-factor GLLVM can be attributed to direction of wording effects in the positive wording of Question (2) while all other questions are negatively worded.

Parameter estimates for the GLLVM were calculated using the *mirt* package in R. Goodness-of-fit statistics were calculated using custom R code for this application.

5 Conclusions

Step-wise testing can be guided by researcher's knowledge about source of lack of fit to produce focused tests with higher power testing model fit to a cross-classified table. The procedure is unconventional because step-wise testing conventionally follows rejection of global null hypothesis first. However, for a high-dimensional cross-classified table, the test of global null hypothesis using X_{PF}^2 is known to have low power, and a step-wise procedure on orthogonal components of X_{PF}^2 as an alternative to the global test can overcome that limitation.

Components of Pearson's Chi-square statistic have a long history in the statistical literature. The present

work on components of Pearson's statistic is in the tradition of Lancaster (1969), Mirvaliev (1987), Raynor and Best (1989) and Eubank(1997).

Calculation of $X_{[t:u]}^2$ is computationally intensive when the number of response variables is large. The computational issues for a large number of binary variables are discussed in detail by Reiser (2019). The dimensions of \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{r} increase exponentially with the number of variables, i.e, c^g , but these are sparse matrices in the sense that most of the entries are zeros. Computations done using the *R* software environment can take advantage of the *sparseMatrix* function to substantially reduce the memory required to hold and perform calculations with these matrices. It is also possible to take advantage of multicore processing in the *R* environment. For a composite null hypothesis, $X_{[t:u]}^2$ requires calculation of the matrix $\mathbf{G} = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\beta}}$, a large matrix with dimension T by g . For a simple null hypothesis, $X_{[t:u]}^2$ does not include the \mathbf{G} matrix, and the amount of random access memory needed for calculation is substantially reduced.

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